

Studies on the Interaction of Metal Ions and Their Hydrous Oxide Sols with Proteins. Part V. Interaction of Aluminium, Iron, Cobalt, Nickel, Silver, and Their Hydrous Oxide Sols with Transfusion Gelatin

Salahuddin and Wahid U. Malik*

pH-titration studies on the interaction of aluminium, cobalt, nickel, and silver ions with transfusion gelatin show the combination of these ions, both from the electrolyte and the sol, with the ionised groups of the protein. The binding of aluminium takes place through the carboxyl groups, whereas imidazole sites are involved in reacting with the rest of the metal ions. The reaction of iron and its hydrous oxide sol with transfusion gelatin is found to be of physical nature.

Previous investigations on metal-protein interaction have shown that metal ions make themselves available for binding to gelatin¹⁻² and transfusion gelatin³⁻⁵, both from the electrolytes and their hydrous oxide sols. These studies have now been extended to include other metal ions, like aluminium, iron, cobalt, nickel, and silver, employing transfusion gelatin as the protein in view of its better characterisation in terms of the number of ionisable groups, heat of ionisation, *pK* value, molecular weight, etc. Corresponding data on the hydrous oxides of these metals have also been included in this communication in order to ascertain the availability of the metal oxides in colloidal state for binding with this particular protein.

EXPERIMENTAL

A 2.0% solution was prepared from transfusion gelatin, as used previously³, and its *pH* was increased to 11.98 by addition of requisite amount of 0.1*N* carbonate-free NaOH⁶.

Sols of the hydrous oxides of the metals were prepared in the same way, as described previously¹⁻², and having the same *pH* and concentration of the respective metal oxides, reported therein.

*Present address: Chemical Laboratories, University of Roorkee, Roorkee.

1. Salahuddin and Malik, this *Journal*, 1962, 39, 693.
2. *Idem*, *ibid.*, 1962, 39, 699.
3. Malik and Salahuddin, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1963, 5, 68; this *Journal*, 1963, 40, 703.
4. *Idem*, *ibid.*, 1963, 4, 147.
5. *Idem*, *Naturwiss.*, 1963, 50, 1.
6. Kolthoff and Sandell, "A Textbook of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd. ed., Macmillan Co, New York, N.Y., 1952, p. 526.

The electrolytic solutions of the respective cations were prepared as reported earlier¹⁻³ and their *pH*s were maintained the same as those for the corresponding hydrous oxide sols.

Procedure.—Varying volumes, viz., 0, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, and 18 ml of the hydrous oxide sols of aluminium, iron, cobalt, nickel, and silver were taken in 50-ml Pyrex conical flasks. Two such sets were arranged; one containing 4 ml of the transfusion gelatin (*pH* 11.98) and the other containing 4 ml of NaOH (*pH* 11.98) solution. The total volume was made to 22 ml in each case. Similar sets were prepared with electrolyte solutions. The *pH* was measured at 25° by a Bockman *pH*-meter, Model G, maintaining an inert atmosphere in the cell.

The interaction of metal ions (available from the metal hydrous oxide sol or the corresponding metal salt) can take place either by competing with hydrogen ions or the hydroxyl ions, depending on the *pH* of the metal-protein systems. In the case of alumina, the resultant *pH* (measured for sodium hydroxide and anionic protein) would represent the concentrations of free hydrogen ions, (H_1) and (H_2), provided by the equations:

$$(H_1) = C_H^+ - C_B \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

$$(H_2) = C_H^+ - (C_B + C_P) \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

$$C_P = (H_1) - (H_2) \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

where C_H^+ represents the total hydrogen-ion concentration in moles/litre present in the sol or electrolyte and C_B is $0.69 \times 10^{-3}M$. A variation in the term C_P therefore can be usefully employed to ascertain the extent of metal-ion binding to the protein, a decrease in its value indicating greater binding of the metal by the protein.

With the hydrous oxide sols of Co, Ni, and Ag existing in the higher *pH* range as compared to alumina, the competition of hydroxyl ions, instead of the hydrogen ions, has to be considered. In this case therefore the following relationships should hold good:

$$C_{F_1} = C - C_{B_1} \quad (4)$$

$$C_{F_2} = C - C_{B_2} \quad (5)$$

where C_{B_1} and C_{B_2} are the amounts of hydroxyl ions (moles/litre) reacting with the metal ion in presence of the protein and the alkali and C is the total amount of hydroxyl ions initially taken. The concentrations of free hydroxyl ions, C_{F_1} and C_{F_2} , may be computed from the corresponding *pH* values, *pH*₁ and *pH*₂. The difference, ΔC_B ($C_{B_1} - C_{B_2}$), at any given *pH* would correspond to the amount of hydroxyl ions competed by the protein in interaction with the metal ion, both from the sol and electrolyte, and therefore may be taken as a measure of metal-ion binding to the protein.

* The values of C_P , C_{B_1} , C_{B_2} , and ΔC_B , thus calculated, are recorded in Tables I-IV. In all the tables protein concentration used was 0.36% (*pH* 11.98).

TABLE I

 Alumina = 6.63 g./litre (pH 1.70). $\text{AlCl}_3 = 4.239 \times 10^{-2} M$. $\text{NaOH} = 0.69 \times 10^{-3} M$.

*H ⁺ added.	Alumina sol.			Aluminium chloride.		
	pH ₁ .	pH ₂ .	**C _p .	pH ₁ .	pH ₂ .	**C _p .
1.627	2.35	1.80	1.139	2.00	2.00	0.000
1.450	2.90	1.90	1.333	2.15	2.00	0.292
1.269	3.56	2.00	0.973	2.80	2.30	0.343
1.086	3.90	2.10	0.782	3.05	2.50	0.227
0.907	4.20	2.18	0.601	3.84	2.90	0.112

 *Expressed in moles/litre $\times 10$.

 **Expressed in moles/litre $\times 10^{-2}$.

TABLE II

 Cobalt oxide = 3.73 g./litre (pH 7.60). $\text{CoCl}_2 = 4.48 \times 10^{-2} M$.

Sol or electrolyte.	Cobalt hydroxide sol.					Cobalt chloride soln.		
	pH ₁ .	pH ₂ .	*C _{B1} .	*C _{B2} .	*ΔC _B .	pH ₁ .	pH ₂ .	*ΔC _B .
18 ml	9.4	9.3	0.679	0.665	0.005	8.50	7.70	0.00266
16	9.4	9.3	0.670	0.665	0.005	8.60	7.70	0.00350
14	9.7	9.5	0.658	0.640	0.018	8.70	7.71	0.00450
12	9.8	9.6	0.650	0.627	0.023	8.72	7.72	0.00470
10	9.8	9.7	0.640	0.627	0.013	8.75	7.75	0.00500
8	10.3	10.0	0.590	0.491	0.099	8.85	7.78	0.00640

 *Expressed in moles/litre $\times 10^3$.

TABLE III

 Nickel oxide sol = 3.81 g./litre (pH 7.6). $\text{NiCl}_2 = 5.62 \times 10^{-2} M$.

Sol or electrolyte.	Nickel oxide sol.					Nickel chloride soln.		
	pH ₁ .	pH ₂ .	*C _{B1} .	C _{B2} .	*ΔC _B .	pH ₁ .	pH ₂ .	*ΔC _B .
18 ml	9.00	8.85	0.683	0.680	0.003	8.80	7.70	0.0058
16	9.00	8.86	0.683	0.680	0.003	8.80	7.70	0.0058
14	9.30	8.88	0.682	0.670	0.012	8.90	7.72	0.0074
12	9.30	9.00	0.680	0.670	0.010	9.00	7.80	0.0094
10	9.35	9.30	0.680	0.667	0.013	9.00	8.04	0.0080
8	9.45	9.60	0.680	0.661	0.019	9.28	9.00	0.0090

*As in Table II.

TABLE IV

$$\text{Ag}_2\text{O} = 9.95 \text{ g./litre (pH 8.30)}. \text{AgNO}_3 = 5.88 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M.}$$

Sol or electrolyte.	Silver oxide sol.					Silver nitrate solution.		
	pH ₁ .	pH ₂ .	*C ₂₁ .	*C ₂₂ .	*ΔC ₂ .	pH ₁ .	pH ₂ .	*ΔC ₂ .
18 ml	9.00	9.80	0.6061	0.6106	0.0163	7.80	6.90	0.0005
16	9.90	9.85	0.6192	0.6106	0.0086	7.80	7.00	0.0005
14	9.95	9.85	0.6192	0.6009	0.0183	7.98	7.20	0.0007
12	10.00	9.95	0.6009	0.5900	0.0109	8.05	7.60	0.0007
10	10.00	9.85	0.6009	0.5900	0.0100	9.25	8.00	0.0007
8	10.15	10.10	0.5640	0.5400	0.0150	10.20	8.15	0.1439
6	10.20	10.15	0.5490	0.5320	0.0170	10.60	10.00	0.2980

*As in Table II.

A rough estimate of the binding of the metal to the protein may be had from the fact that the anionic transfusion gelatin brings about coagulation of the hydrous oxide sols at pHs sufficiently higher than those for the corresponding NaOH-hydrous oxide sol mixtures. The pH for the onset of precipitation⁷ of the metal ions (3.9 for Al³⁺, 7.7 for Co²⁺, 7.7 for Ni²⁺, and 9.1 for Ag⁺) increases to 4.5, 9.0, 9.6, and 10.20 respectively. These observations infer the possibility of some sort of chemical reaction⁸ between the protein and the metal ion.

DISCUSSION

The competing tendency of aluminium ions is self-evident from the pH-titration curve of the protein (Fig. 1). The curves, both for alumina and aluminium chloride, lie well

FIG. 1.

Curves A; E : For sol and the protein.
 B; G : " Electrolyte "
 C; H : " " NaOH
 D; F : " Sol "

above those for the alkali; besides, the curves are markedly flat in the pH range 3.0-4.2. All these facts lend support to the view that the carboxyl groups of the protein make themselves available for combination with the metal ion since the pH value of the group in this particular protein is 4.7. Our earlier studies¹⁻⁵ also go in favour of these results since transfusion gelatin shows no appreciable binding for the hydrogen¹ and chloride ions⁹ in the pH range under discussion. Assuming that non-specific factors like adsorption would not be operative below pH 4.7 (due to electrostatic repulsion), the shifts in pH can be attributed

7. Gurd and Wilcox, "Advances in Protein Chemistry", 1956, vol 11, 324.

8. Weiser, "Textbook of Colloid Chemistry", John Wiley and Sons, N. Y., 1949, p. 297; see also J. S.

Fruton and S. Simmonds, "General Biochemistry", Asia Publishing House, Bombay, 2nd ed., 1962, p. 21.

9. Carr, *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1953, 46, 417.

only to the binding of the metal ion by the protein. The decrease in ΔC_B values to $0.60 \times 10^{-2} M$ on increasing the pH (4.20 and 3.84) for the sol and the metal ion respectively (Table I) also indicates that more of hydrogen ions are displaced in view of greater metal-ion binding by the protein at higher pH .

The pH -titration curves of transfusion gelatin in presence of increasing amounts of cobalt, nickel, and silver salts as well as for mixtures containing varying amounts of the respective hydroxide sol exhibit almost a similar nature, the curves for NaOH lying below those for the protein in each case (Fig. 2). The constancy in pH -titration curves (Fig. 2,

FIG 2

Curves A_1 , A_2 and A_3 for sol + protein.
 B_1 , B_2 " B_3 " " + NaOH.
 C_1 , C_2 " C_3 " electrolyte + protein.
 d_1 , d_2 " d_3 " " + NaOH.

for the silver sol, however, provide enough evidence for the binding of silver ion by the protein.

Results on the intraction of cobalt, nickel, and silver salts with transfusion gelatin, as evidenced from the titration curves, provide clue to another sort of binding, possible in the case of this particular protein. From curves C_1 and C_3 (Fig. 2), the flat portions of the titration curves lie in the pH range (8.5-8.75 and 7.8-9.05 for Co^{2+} and Ag^+) where almost all the imidazole groups are available for metal-ion binding and only a few amino groups can be made available for this purpose. Such a behaviour is not surprising in view of the marked tendency of cobalt ions for reaction with histidine¹⁰.

The variations in C_B values with pH are remarkably significant in the case of silver ions. From Table IV it would be observed that ΔC_B does not change in the pH range 7.80 to 9.25, but a sudden increase from 0.06 mM to 0.14 mM is observed beyond this pH . These results (so also those for the Co^{2+} ion) reveal that the metal ion is preferentially bound through the imidazole sites of transfusion gelatin. The behaviour of nickel appears to be

curves A_1 , A_2 , and A_3) in the pH range 8.0-9.5 (for hydroxide sols of Co, Ni, and Ag) indicates that the binding of the metal ions with the amino group of the protein is possible. From the variations in ΔC_B values with pH , an estimate of the extent of the protein competing with its free hydroxyl ions for the reaction with metal ions can be made. Thus in the case of cobalt and nickel hydroxide sols, the values of ΔC_B increased from 0.005 mM to 0.013 mM and from 0.003 mM to 0.019 mM respectively for increase of 0.4 unit in pH . Since in the case of silver oxide sol investigations could not be carried out below pH 10.0 and in the vicinity of this pH all the available amino groups of the transfusion gelatin are free for interaction with the metal, no variation in ΔC_B values could be observed in the pH range of 9.9-10.20. The values of ΔC_B

different since the well-defined flat portion of the titration curve (Fig. 2, curve C_2) lies only in the vicinity of pH 9.0 and ΔC_B values exhibit almost consistent increase with increase in pH values (Table III). These observations can be interpreted in terms of the binding of nickel ion primarily through the amino groups of transfusion gelatin. Moreover, from the ΔC_B values it may be concluded that unlike gelatin, this protein binds more nickel than either cobalt or silver.

The pH-titration curves for iron (Fig. 1, curves G or H) do not provide any information regarding the binding of iron by the protein since the curve for protein almost coincides with that of the alkali. A flat portion makes its appearance in the neighbourhood of pH 8.0 for titration curve of ferric oxide sol. Since very few amino groups are likely to make themselves free for reaction with the protein in this pH range, the interaction of the two may be taken as a purely physical phenomenon.

Thanks are due to professor A. R. Kidwai for providing laboratory facilities and to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a fellowship to one of the authors (S).